

19/5/68

as from. Pembroke College

OXFORD.

Dear Bill

I arrived back in England on 21st of April and it seems to have drizzled (very appropriately I think that this is English, English slang is - it rained very ~~little~~ gently but continuously) ever since. So I've had no hunting on the Thames or any of the ~~hunting~~ things I looked forward to, but things must improve.

Being a brave fool I'm going to classes where I read the Vulgate with some linguists studying Persian. My excavation, kitchen, vocabulary could not be more inappropriate for such a task, but I'm learning.

Otherwise I've been steadily wading through Islamic site reports and beginning to prepare the ground for my next story in Iran: I hope to buy myself a Land Rover. I'm applying to every organization I can think of to help me

raise the money. I hope to stay - Iran from late July to May 1969 doing a field survey of major historic sites in Kerman, and the Khamak of Malesh in Fars. Many of the sites can be identified on maps etc from the written sources - place names etc. It is an area where I ought to really get the two basic early Islamic pottery traditions (Thorasian, and Mesopotamian) and their interaction, apart from the considerable interest of the later waves.

But how are things with you. I take it that you will be able to stay another year - Shiraz. Will you be able to make the roadages you hoped to do? How is the family? It must be getting quite hot now in Shiraz.

In my work I've kept my eyes very much open for Islamic painted wares, and I'm building up a considerable number of sites. Briefly during the "13, 14, 15 C" a very developed painted ware virtually if not exclusively in the form of jugs has been found in great ^{quantities} ~~numbers~~ especially in Syria, Palestine, and the Persian Gulf down to Makran, ~~(with no museum etc)~~ ^(but very different from the Syrian wares) probably any development on the Iranian plateau outside Fars was very limited. In the earlier Islamic period c 10 c AD there was a very simple

underdeveloped painted ware in small quantities - Syria and Palestine
probably derived from the late Roman painted wares, but completely
different from the elaborate thin line decoration of the later pieces.
At Karkhori Bagasar in Afghanistan there is one piece of developed
painted ware ~~not~~ well dated to the 11th or 11c AD which I would
dismiss as a freak (it has an extraordinary ornamentation network
shape) use it not for hearsay accounts of ware. Moreover in
Italy it seems that the Islamic thin line painted ware replaced
the later Roman type painted in the 10c or 11c (though of course
this ware is Italian 'Islamic' ware is very different from that - Far.
Maaser Schmidt found some developed painted ~~to~~ ware -
Italish. I suspect that these might be late Italish (ie 10-11c) the
same time as the introduction of late painted wares into Italy, on
the grounds that these shards are absent from Siraf period II (but
then of course your painted wares have no echo on the coast
among contemporary (though much poorer) collections of Siraf IV)

Well as you can gather from this near-ignores and quite
unfavorably long reply I'm still very much thinking about your
pottery - but I must catch the post.

Do keep me informed on the news.

My regards to Frances and the children

Yours

Andy